

Prevalence and Predictors of Fear of Missing Out among University Students

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Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) is characterized by the anxiety of being left out of social experiences and events, often exacerbated by the ongoing exposure to glorified portrayals of others' lives on social media platforms (Przybylski et al., 2013). This study investigated the prevalence and predictors of fear of missing out among university students in Ghana. Convenience sampling was used in the cross-sectional descriptive survey to select 442 University of Cape Coast respondents. The study's findings showed that among university students, FOMO was prevalent at moderate (46.2%) and low levels (53.8%). More than half of the students had high self-esteem, and a significant number also had medium and low self-esteem. Most university students were found to have moderately high levels of loneliness. According to the study, among university students, loneliness and self-esteem were significant predictors of FOMO. The association between loneliness and FOMO was not significantly moderated by sex, but the relationship between self-esteem and FOMO was. It was recommended that the National Communications Authority, Ghana Psychology Council and Educational Institutions collaborate in putting measures that regulate the social media usage as well as building self-esteem in students by creating programs focused on healthy social interactions.

Keywords: Fear of missing out (FOMO), self-esteem, loneliness, sex, university students

In the modern era of digital connectivity, the global influence of social media networks has changed the social interaction and communication dynamics of young people, especially university students (Kwok & Wescott, 2020). Among the various consequences of this transition, one phenomenon that has received a lot of attention is "fear of missing out" (FOMO). FOMO represents a widespread and growing concern. In today's ultra-connected society, affecting individuals across diverse demographic groups. It is particularly relevant and pronounced among university students who have been raised in the era of social media and instant communication (Manca, 2020). University students' propensity for FOMO is both a reflection of and a response to the evolving nature of social interaction, as they are often among the first to adopt new platforms and technological advancements. Ghana's social media use as of 2022 was 8.8 million, which was equivalent to 27.4% of the total population, compared to 8.2 million, which was equivalent to 26.1% of the population by 2021 (DataReportal, 2022). The analysis revealed that social media users in Ghana increased by 600 thousand, which is 1.3% between 2021 and 2022. These statistics show the margin of people who are active social media users and the probability of these users

experiencing higher levels of FOMO (Topino et al., 2023). A quarter of all internet users worldwide have FOMO, which is a developing concern (O'Connell, 2020). From 2018 to the present, the percentage of persons who spend more than 10 hours a day online has risen from 2.8% to 5.4% (Elhai et al., 2021). For university students in Ghana, who are becoming more and more accustomed to living in a technologically advanced environment (Qua-Enoo et al., 2021) FOMO may have a serious negative impact on their mental well-being, scholastic achievement, and overall college experience. Research indicates that FOMO victims are more prone to experience stress, anxiety, and life dissatisfaction (Tanhan et al., 2022). This can cause maladaptive issues such as substance abuse and risky sexual practices as well as thoughts of worthlessness or hopelessness which can affect one's self esteem and loneliness. Self-esteem and loneliness are recognized as significant predictors of FOMO (Uram & Skalski, 2022). Most studies conducted on FOMO can be found in the USA (Hetz et al., 2015; Hodkinson, 2019; Debb et al., 2022), Europe (Aygul & Akbay, 2019; Popovac & Hadlington, 2020), Asia (Chang & Chen, 2019; Lee et al., 2020; Kim & Lee, 2021; Koo & Kwon, 2019), and some parts of Africa, specifically South Africa, Nigeria, Zambia and Egypt (Jood, 2017; Omodior, 2021; Mambwe, 2018; Awad et al., 2020). Researchers in Ghana have studied the relationship between internet addiction and social media use (Kyei & Nsiah, 2019; Gyasi & Aikins, 2021) as well as the correlation between social media addiction and academic performance, self-esteem, and overall mental health (Boateng, 2018; Adu-Gyamfi et al., 2019; Adjei & Armah, 2021). It is crucial to bridge the gaps in existing research and shed light on the ecological and literature aspects of this issue.

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Review of Literature

Prevalence of FOMO

Globally, literature reveals that research done on the prevalence of FOMO among university students remains limited (Li et al., 2020;

Milyavskaya et al., 2018; Qutishat & Abu Sharour, 2019). None of these studies was conducted in West Africa. For instance, In the study by Milyavskaya et al. (2018) also found that only 13% of their university students in Canada never experienced FOMO implying that 87% of university students recorded high level of FOMO. In Jordan, Qutishat, and Abu Sharour (2019) reported a moderate FOMO mean score of 28.9 among university students. In comparison, Li et al. (2020) discovered that 15.2% of participants experienced severe FOMO among university students in China. In another study that used young adults by Przybylski et al. (2013) found that approximately 70% of United Kingdom (UK) university students reported experiencing FOMO. These variations in prevalence rates may reflect differences in cultural context, measurement tools, sample and sampling techniques. In view of this, no study has examined the prevalence of FOMO among university students in Ghana.

FoMO and Self-esteem

To date, it appears that there is no existing study that has examined the influence of FOMO on self-esteem among university students. Existing studies have looked at the relationship between FOMO and self-esteem among adolescents which typically reflects high school students (Barry & Wong's, 2020; Buglass et al., 2017) and young adults (Przybylski et al., 2013; Kuss & Griffiths, 2017). In view of empirical studies done using adolescents, for example, Buglass et al. (2017) identified an association between FOMO and self-esteem. Also, Wisudawati and Aqmarina (2022) found that adolescents who experienced higher levels of FOMO reported significantly lower self-esteem. Moreover, in the study by Przybylski et al. (2013) discovered a negative link between self-esteem and FOMO. Thus, people who had lower self-esteem were more prone to experiencing FOMO. Geographically, it appears that these reported studies have been done in Turkey (Darcin et al., 2016), United Kingdom ((Buglass et al., 2017; Przybylski et al., 2013; Kuss & Griffiths, 2017), Indonesia (Wisudawati & Aqmarina, 2022) with no studies appearing to be done in Ghana.

It is obvious that studies on the influence of FOMO on loneliness among university students are almost non-existent in the literature. However, past studies have shown the association between FOMO and loneliness among university students (Abel et al., 2016; Arifiani & Mahanani, 2021; Huynh et al., 2022; Wan & Zhou, 2025). This evidenced from studies by Huynh et al. (2022) who recorded a positive relationship between FOMO and loneliness among Vietnamese undergraduate students. Therefore, those with elevated levels of FOMO likewise experienced significant levels of loneliness. Moreover, Wan and Zhou (2025) found that loneliness was linked to higher FOMO, and social media use mediated this influence on FOMO among Chinese university students. Furthermore, Arifiani and Mahanani (2021) recorded a positive significant correlation between loneliness and FOMO among university students. Given the reported findings, it appears that no study has yet been done in Ghana as existing studies have been done in China (Wan & Zhou, 2025), Vietnamese (Huynh et al., 2022), and Indonesia (Arifiani & Mahanani, 2021) Hence, this study seeks to ascertain whether FOMO will influence Loneliness among university students in Ghana.

Moderating Role of Sex in the Relationship between Self-esteem and FOMO

However, no research has been done to look at how sex affects the

association of university students' self-esteem and FOMO. One study looked at the predictive influence of sex on FOMO among university students (Mewafarosh et al., 2024). It was found that sex predicted FOMO among Chinese university students (Mewafarosh et al., 2024). Moreover, related studies have been done to look at the relationship between sex and FOMO (Kanoosh, 2023; Mihci & Gezgin, 2021; Qutishat, 2020; Wireko, 2019). For instance, Qutishat (2020) demonstrated significant gender differences with regard to FOMO among Oman university students. Kanoosh (2023) noted in his study that female revealed greater levels of FOMO in comparison to male university students in Jordan. Also, Wireko (2019) found that sex differences were found in FOMO levels among Ghanaian University students. Contrary, in one study by Mihci and Gezgin (2021) found that there was no difference in terms of FOMO according to sex. Furthermore, it appears that a relatively few studies have been done on the relationship between sex and self-esteem among university students (Achak et al., 2025; Adrick & Mauki, 2023; Bermejo-Cantarero et al., 2025; Olatunbosun & Pillay, 2025) Bermejo-Cantarero et al. (2025) reported that self-esteem differences of Spanish university students were not statistically significant in regard to gender considering lifestyle. Moreso, Achak et al. (2025) noted on the fact that male showed significantly higher self-esteem than female Moroccan university students. Additionally, in the study by (Adrick & Mauki, 2023) using Tanzanian students results showed that male had better self-esteem than their female counterparts. The possible relationships between sex, self-esteem and FOMO suggest that sex can also control the interaction of self-esteem and FOMO among university students. Since past studies did not examine this issue, the present seeks to fill the gap.

Moderating Role of Sex in the Relationship between Loneliness and FOMO

No study has been done to examine the moderating role of sex in the relationship between self-esteem and FOMO among university students. One study looked at the predictive influence of sex on FOMO among university students (Mewafarosh et al., 2024). It was found that sex predicted FoMO among Chinese university students (Mewafarosh et al., 2024). Moreover, related studies have been done to look at the relationship between sex and FOMO (Kanoosh, 2023; Mihci & Gezgin, 2021; Qutishat, 2020; Wireko, 2019). For instance, Qutishat (2020) demonstrated significant gender differences with regard to FOMO among Oman university students. Kanoosh (2023) noted in his study that female reported elevated levels of FOMO as opposed to male university students in Jordan. Also in the study by Wireko (2019) found that sex differences were found in FOMO levels among Ghanaian University students. Contrary, in one study by Mihci and Gezgin (2021) found that there was no difference in terms of FOMO according to sex. Nevertheless, research on the relationship between sex and loneliness among university students appears limited in literature (Başoğlu, 2019; Chura-Quispe et al., 2025; Kim, 2001; Zhang et al., 2020). Chura-Quispe et al. (2025) in their study found that male students showed significantly higher levels of loneliness than female students. Also, Başoğlu (2019) found that gender was significantly related to loneliness among Turkey university students. Thus, male students had higher total loneliness than females' students. Kim (2001) found that females scored higher on loneliness as compared to male students highlighting a significant difference. Nevertheless, these reported studies have shown consistency in their findings given that there is a

significance differences in gender with regard to loneliness among university students even though, there are mixed findings as to males scoring higher levels than females and the vice versa (Başoğlu, 2019; Chura-Quispe et al., 2025; Kim, 2001; Zhang et al., 2020). The possible relationships between sex, loneliness and FOMO suggest that sex can moderate the relationship between Loneliness and FOMO among university students. Since past studies did not examine this issue, the current study seeks to fill the unknown.

Figure 1

Hypothetical Model

Method

Design and Participants

The researcher used a quantitative approach, more precisely a descriptive cross-sectional survey design. The research's target group consisted of all university students in Ghana. The University of Cape Coast's regular undergraduate students made up the accessible population with the focus on students from level 100 to 400, across all halls of residence. According to the student's records of UCC, there is a total of 15,721 male students and 11,767 female students, making a total student population of 27,488 regular undergraduate students. 487 respondents in total were selected as a sample size from the study's accessible population. The Yamane formula provides justification for this figure. With the Yamane formula, $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e^2)}$ where N is population size and e is level of precision. Using this formula, a calculated sample of, $n = \frac{27488}{1+27488(0.0025)^2}$, 442 with an additional 10% non-response rate was selected among the whole population of students with an error margin of 5%, with a 95% confidence level. Participants were chosen using the convenience sample technique.

Inclusion Criteria

- Only regular undergraduate students were eligible for the study.
- Students who owned portable smart devices.
- Active social media users with one or more accounts on WhatsApp, Instagram, Twitter, or Facebook

Exclusion Criteria

- Respondents who are not regular undergraduate students were excluded from the study.
- Students who do not own a smart portable device.
- Individuals without access to social media or who do not use it regularly

Measures

Fear of Missing Out Scale: The Fear of Missing Out scale (Przybylski et al., 2013) is made up ten items. A 5-point scale, with 1 denoting "Not at all true of me" and 5 denoting "Extremely true of me," was used to positively anchor responses to items such as "I fear others have more rewarding experiences than me." An average score between one and five was obtained using the scale. Higher scores

indicate that students' experiences of FOMO is high. The scores range from 10 to 50. Moderate (2437), high (3850), and low (1023). A reliability score (Cronbach's $\alpha = .88$) was obtained by running reliability for the FOMO scale, supporting earlier research (Przybylski et al., 2013).

The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale: Rosenberg (1965) developed the scale. This 10-item uni-dimensional scale was measured on a 4-point Likert scale, ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Scores range from low (1025), medium (2629) and high (3040). The scale had an internal consistency of .92.

UCLA Loneliness Scale (Version 3): Daniel Russell created the UCLA Loneliness Scale in 1996. It is a 20-item measure meant to find an individual's experiences of social isolation and loneliness. Either O ("I often feel this way"), S ("I sometimes feel this way"), R ("I rarely feel this way"), or N ("I never feel this way") are the ratings given by participants to each item. The possible score is between 20 and 80. A range of 2034 represents a low level of loneliness, 3549 a moderate level, 5064 a moderately high level, and 6580 a high level. The scale shows good internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.71.

Ethical Consideration, Data Collection, and Procedure

In order to safeguard research respondents' interests, the environment, the community, and the industry, and avoid risking the individuals being studied, the researcher applied to UCC's Institutional Review Board (UCCIRB) for approval to carry out the field study. Protocol was given for the field study to be carried out with IRB number CES/ERB/UCC/edu/v8-23/72. The researcher attached an introductory letter to Google Forms that contained the questionnaires to be responded to. The researcher located the respondents using their various social media platforms. With the respondents, the goals of the study and the ethical issues were fairly discussed in the google forms. An option to decline participation was provided. Confidentiality of information was assured to the respondents. The questionnaire contained explicit instructions on how the items were to be answered. Respondents were made aware that they can contact the principal investigator to ask for clarification pertaining to any of the questions they did not understand. No individual was held under coercion to be a participant in the study. To gather the necessary data, questionnaires with the various study scales were posted on the respondents' social media platforms by contacting the class representatives and permission sought before the link to the google forms were sent out. The google forms allowed ample time for respondents to finish the questionnaire. Data was collected in the span of one and a half months, with a response rate of 99% and a 1% decline.

Data Analysis

The first stage of the data processing was editing all the responses derived from the questionnaires that the respondents gave. This was done to check for any omissions and that the questionnaires were correctly responded to, without making any alterations to the responses. After the editing was completed, the data was extracted from the Excel of the Google Forms and onto SPSS version 26. For the coding process, numerical values were assigned to all the variables in the questionnaire before the analysis was done. Reliability analysis was first run against the sample of the study to ascertain the reliability of the various instruments. The FOMO scale had a Cronbach's alpha of .87, UCLA loneliness scale was .91 and

Rosenberg Self-esteem scale was .71. Composite scores of the various instruments were computed and used to run the analysis. The demographic data from the research was analysed using frequencies and percentages. Frequencies and percentages were utilized to answer research questions one (1) to three (3). The first and second research hypotheses were tested using linear regression. Using Hayes Process Macro, a moderation analysis was carried out for hypotheses three (3) and four (4).

Results

Table 1

Demographic Information

Sex	Frequency	Percent (%)
Male	252	57.0
Female	190	43.0

Table 1 displays the result, which indicates that 43% of respondents were female and 57% of respondents were male.

Table 2

Prevalence of Fear of Missing Out (FOMO)

Sex	Frequency	Percent (%)
Low	238	53.8
Moderate	204	46.2

Findings shows that the level of FOMO was prevalent among 53.8% of the students while moderate level prevalent in 46.2% of them.

Figure 2

Observed Conceptual Framework

Table 3

Predictive Relationship between Self-esteem and FoMo

	B	S.E	B	t	Sig.
(Constant)	37.163	1.716		21.658	.000
Self-esteem	-.470	.055	-.377	-8.551	.000

Note. All statistical tests were conducted at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$

A linear regression was performed to determine the predictive relationship between self-esteem and FOMO. Regression model $F(1,440) = 73.122, p < .001$, indicated statistical significance. The variance in FOMO was explained by the model to be 14.3%. The result from table 5 indicated that self-esteem significantly predicted FOMO ($\beta = -.377, p < .001$). This suggests that when students have high level self-esteem, they are less prone to feel the fear of being left out.

To determine the predictive relationship between loneliness and FOMO, a linear regression analysis was conducted. At $F(1,440) = 21.442, p < .001$, the regression model was statistically significant.

FOMO variance was explained by the model to the tune of 4.6%. The results from table 6 revealed that loneliness significantly predicted FOMO ($\beta = .216, p < .001$). This suggests that when students are lonely, a greater likelihood of FOMO is experienced by them.

Table 4

Predictive Relationship between Loneliness and FoMo

	B	S.E	B	t	Sig.
(Constant)	12.580	2.203		5.711	.000
Self-esteem	.188	.041	.216	4.631	.000

Note. All statistical tests were conducted at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$

Table 5

Interaction Effect of Sex on the Relationship between Self-esteem and FoMo

	B	SEB	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	53.23	5.29	10.07	.00	42.84	63.62
Self-esteem	-.90	.17	-5.31	.00	-1.23	-.56
Sex	-10.67	3.37	-3.17	.00	-17.28	-4.05
Int_1	.28	0.11	2.60	.01	.07	.49
Conditional effects of the focal predictor at values of the moderator(s)						
Male	-.62	.07	-8.22	.00	-.76	-.47
Female	-.34	.08	-4.32	.00	-.49	-.18

Note. Model Summary: $R^2 = .18; F(3,438) = 32.13, p = .00$, Int_1: Self-esteem * Sex: $R^2\text{-chg} = .01; F(1,438) = 6.75, p = .01$

Criterion: FOMO

The result as presented in Table 5 above indicates that sex reduces the likelihood of students experiencing FOMO ($B = -10.67, p = .03$). The association that exists between self-esteem and FOMO is significantly moderated by sex [$B = .28, t = 2.60, CI (.07, .49), p = .01$]. The results suggest that sex augments, mitigates, or oppose how self-esteem relates to FOMO. The conditional effects of RSE on FOMO at different values of Sex are shown in the Table 5. As shown in the table, the effect of RSE on FOMO is stronger for males than for females. To interpret the interaction term, we can look at the conditional effects of RSE on FOMO at different values of sex. The results in the output shows that for males, an increase of one unit in self-esteem corresponds to a reduction of 0.62 units in FOMO ($t = -8.22, p = .00$). For females, an increase of one unit in self-esteem is linked to 0.34-unit reduction units in FOMO ($t = -4.32, p = .00$). This means that an increase in self-esteem has a stronger impact on lowering FOMO in males as compared to females.

Table 6

Interaction Effect of Sex on the Relationship between Loneliness and FOMO

	B	SEB	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	15.46	6.57	2.35	.02	2.55	28.37
Loneliness	.19	.12	1.60	.11	-.05	.43
Sex	-2.90	4.66	-.62	.53	-12.07	6.27
Int_1	.01	.09	.14	.89	-.16	.25

Note. Model Summary: $R^2 = .08; F(3,438) = 12.03, p = .00$, Int_1: Loneliness * Sex: $R^2\text{-chg} = .00; F(1,438) = .02, p = .82$

Criterion: FOMO

The result as presented in Table 6, implies that sex does

not significantly affect the link between FOMO and loneliness [$B = .01, t = .14, CI (-.16, .25), p = .89$]. The results suggest that sex does not augment, mitigate, or oppose how loneliness relates to FOMO.

Discussion

According to the findings from research question one, a significant percentage of university students report experiencing FOMO. This might be a result of the hectic schedules of extracurricular activities, social events, and academic obligations that characterize university life such as academic opportunities, social gatherings, or even the newest trends. This result corroborates with a study from Milyavskaya et al. (2018) who found that 15% of the sample experienced it once a week or more often. Furthermore, 35% of respondents said they experienced FOMO one to three times per month, 36% said they experienced it less frequently than once per month, and only 13% said they had never experienced it. Also, Przybylski et al. (2013) reported that approximately 70% of participants said they had experienced FOMO. According to Trottier (2016), the result of the research question may indicate that the increased prevalence of FOMO in the setting of university life is a result of the unparalleled accessibility of social media platforms and digital communication, which provide continuous exposure to peer activities and social events in real time. This heightened exposure, coupled with the innate human desire for social connectedness and acceptance, has paved the way for FOMO to emerge as a prevalent emotional state among the university student population.

Moreover, research hypothesis one aimed to ascertain whether self-esteem predicts FOMO. The findings show that self-esteem and FOMO have a negative predictive relationship. It is implied by a negative predictive relationship between self-esteem and FOMO that FOMO tends to decrease with increasing self-esteem and vice versa. In simple terms, people who have higher self-esteem tend to be less prone to FOMO, whereas people who have lower self-esteem are more likely to experience it. This finding is supported by Buglass et al. (2017) who found a link between FOMO and lower self-esteem. In addition, Barry and Wong's (2020) also discovered a significant relationship between FOMO and high levels of loneliness, low self-esteem, and low self-compassion. This suggests that FOMO is more prevalent in people with lower self-esteem, possibly because of feelings of inadequacy or a greater need for validation from others. These results suggest that self-esteem might function as an impediment to the onset of FOMO. Higher self-esteem is associated with a more positive self-concept, increased self-assurance, and a stronger sense of self-worth (Kim & Lee, 2021). This, in turn, may reduce their need for constant social validation and their fear of being left out or missing out on social experiences.

Moreover, research hypothesis two sought to investigate whether loneliness does predict FOMO. The results indicate that loneliness positively predicts FOMO, implying that university students who experience greater loneliness are more likely to experience FOMO. A positive predictive relationship suggests that as loneliness increases, so does FOMO. This means that individuals with higher levels of loneliness also have higher experiences of FOMO. The results imply that loneliness can act as a precursor or trigger for FOMO. Feelings of social disconnection and isolation are common components of loneliness (Rokach, 2018). This finding is in line with Huynh et al. (2022) who found a positive relationship between FOMO and loneliness among Vietnamese undergraduate students.

Thus, students who exhibited high level of FOMO also had high level of loneliness. This was also supported by Wan and Zhou (2025) who found that loneliness was linked to higher FOMO among Chinese university students. Furthermore, Arifiani and Mahanani (2021) recorded a positive significant correlation between loneliness and FOMO among university students. The positive predictive relationship between these constructs highlights the potential for a cascade effect, where loneliness may lead to heightened FOMO, which, in turn, exacerbates negative emotional states. When people compare their lives to those of others who appear to have perfect lives, social comparison can have detrimental effects on such individuals that are exacerbated by loneliness (Cramer et al., 2016). Social media frequently facilitates this kind of social comparison, which can be a potent FOMO trigger.

Furthermore, research hypothesis three sought to find out whether sex moderates the link that exists between self-esteem and FOMO. This happens to be a novel finding. Finding in this analysis demonstrated that sex appears to influence how self-esteem relates to FOMO. The interaction effect signifies that sex plays a role in shaping the impact of self-esteem on FOMO. When examining the conditional effects, it is clear that self-esteem has a more pronounced effect on reducing FOMO in males compared to females. This means that an increase in self-esteem has a stronger impact on lowering FOMO in males as compared to females. These findings highlight that sex has a significant role in how self-esteem influences FOMO.

Finally, research hypothesis four sought to inquire if sex moderates the relationship between loneliness and FOMO. This finding is also said to be the first of its kind, hence adding to the literature gap. The findings suggest that there is no significant moderating effect of sex on the relationship between FOMO and loneliness. Sex does not appear to significantly influence how loneliness relates to FOMO and the experience of loneliness and FOMO may not vary substantially between male and female individuals. The absence of sex as a significant moderator highlights the universal nature of emotional experiences such as loneliness and FOMO. It underscores the idea that these psychological states can transcend gender differences and may be influenced by similar underlying mechanisms and social dynamics across diverse gender groups.

Limitations of the Study

The primary constraint of the research was the utilization of Google Forms to gather data from the intended respondents. Getting students to respond to the questionnaire online was a hassle since most of them would ignore opening the link as soon as they see the message. To mitigate this limitation, respondents were contacted personally, and made sure they understood the goal of the study in order to get their responses. Second, Participants were drawn from a single institution (University of Cape Coast), and therefore, results may not apply broadly to all university students in Ghana or other geographical contexts. Third, relying on self-reported data may have resulted in response biases. Participants might have reported less or more than their true experiences which could affect the findings' accuracy.

Conclusion

The study also found that a significant percentage of university students report experiencing FOMO. Both self-esteem and loneliness could predict the level of FOMO university students felt.

Additionally, sex played a role in how self-esteem and FOMO were connected, but it did not significantly affect the relationship between loneliness and FOMO. These findings really underline the need to pay attention to issues like low self-esteem, which can be improved through self-awareness and activities that help build confidence. Tackling loneliness by encouraging meaningful social connections and emotional support is also key. Overall, this study makes it clear that we need more research to better understand FOMO, especially in the university setting.

Recommendations

We recommend that as part of the interventions to mitigate FOMO, National Communications Authority (NCA) should collaborate with educational institutions and mental health experts to develop and implement public awareness campaigns regarding responsible and balanced use of technology, including social media. Also, the Ghana Psychology Council (GPC) should integrate FOMO related topics into seminars and CPD programs to ensure that mental health professionals are well-equipped to understand and address FOMO in their practice. Furthermore, I recommend that universities create peer support and mentorship programs that encourage students networking.

Suggestion for Further Research

Future research can take a qualitative approach, utilizing focus groups or in-depth interviews. This can provide valuable context to qualitative findings. Additionally, research can contrast the frequency and contributing factors of FOMO in college students from various cultural backgrounds and regions within Ghana. This can shed light on the impact of cultural diversity on FOMO.

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